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Vehicle routing with stochastic demand, service and waiting times — The case of food bank collection problems

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ABSTRACT

Food banks play an important role both in combating food waste, and in alleviating hunger. However, due to the many uncertainties that food banks face, they often struggle to effectively collect all food items that donors such as supermarkets are willing to provide. To tackle this problem, we introduce the capacitated vehicle routing problem with travel time restrictions and stochastic demand, service and waiting times, in which the uncertainties are dependent of each other. This problem can be generalized to a large variety of routing applications. The goal of the problem is to determine a minimum number of vehicles, and to plan cost-effective routes for these vehicles so that each route violates the vehicle capacity and the travel time limit with only a very small probability. The resulting problem is highly complex and thus solved by means of a matheuristic, which decomposes the problem into its natural decision components. Thus, it first determines the number of districts into which the service area should be partitioned, before allocating each customer to exactly one district and then plans a route for each district. A set of feedback mechanisms is activated whenever no feasible solution has been found through these steps. Extensive numerical experiments, involving both randomly generated and real-life instances, demonstrate the matheuristic's effectiveness in solving instances with up to 100 customers. When applying our matheuristic to real-life instances from Dutch and Canadian food banks, we furthermore gain managerial insights to assist in optimizing fleet size and route cost.

1. Introduction

Today, 17% of all food that reaches the consumer level (at home, in restaurants, or at grocery stores) is wasted (United Nations, 2022). At the same time, a rising number of people, currently estimated at 700 million, are food-insecure, which means that they cannot rely on having an adequate meal every day, and they regularly go to bed hungry (FAO et al., 2021). Achieving food security and reducing food waste are integral parts of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, as specified in Targets 2.1 and 12.3, respectively. The link between these two goals is apparent, since reducing food waste ensures, in principle, that more resources become available to meet the needs of vulnerable people who are acutely food-insecure. However, the redistribution of resources is often challenging, and food waste prevention at the retail stage can have unintended negative effects on redistribution initiatives at the end of the chains led by organizations such as food banks and soup kitchens.

Being largely dependent on donations from food retailers and restaurants, the European association of food banks FEBA signals,

in this context, a structural decline in donations due to successful food waste prevention efforts at retailers, leaving fewer products to be donated to food banks (European Food Banks Federation, 2022). At the same time, the number of active beneficiaries of food banks is rising due to, among other factors, high inflation levels, putting increasing pressure on food bank operations and on the associated redistribution efforts. Given these pressures, it is crucial for food banks to improve their decision making and streamline their operations in order to optimize redistribution activities and fully utilize the available resources. Transport and logistics remain a major challenge in this context, as highlighted in the recent review of Akkerman et al. (2023). One of the main reasons for this is that efficient route planning, which helps make good use of the available capacities, is often hampered by different types of uncertainty which complicate the decision making. In practice, uncertainty affects several aspects of the problem, such as the quantities donated, the waiting times, the loading times, and the availability of drivers. Focusing on operational real-world challenges in humanitarian logistics, such as the role of uncertainty, Besiou et al.

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(2018) illustrate the potential of operations research models in this context.

Inspired by these considerations, this research attempts to capture the uncertain decision environment associated with food bank operations and improve the decision making, giving rise to the Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem (CVRP) with travel time restrictions, stochastic demand, service and waiting times (CVRP-SDSW). The CVRP-SDSW incorporates two types of decisions: strategic choices for designing delivery districts, which cannot be revised regularly, and operational choices regarding the vehicle route associated with each district, which can be adjusted more easily. The goal of the problem is to determine a minimum number of vehicles (equal to the number of districts in our context), and to plan cost-effective routes for these vehicles, so that each customer location is visited and each route is ‘feasible’, i.e., each route violates the vehicle capacity and the travel time limit with only a very small probability. The stochasticity in the demand and in the service and waiting times at the customer locations makes the problem highly complex. The problem is therefore solved by means of a matheuristic, i.e., a “heuristic algorithm [] made by the interoperation of metaheuristics and mathematical programming techniques” (Boschetti et al., 2009), which decomposes the problem into its individual decision components to obtain a feasible solution. Thus, it first determines the number of districts, before allocating each customer to exactly one district and then plans a route for each district. The matheuristic enters a set of feedback mechanisms whenever no feasible solution has been found through these steps. Extensive experiments are carried out to test the computational performance of the matheuristic on a set of benchmark instances derived from the well-known instances of Solomon (1987). In addition, we investigate the impact of different levels of uncertainty and gain valuable managerial insights by applying our methodology to several real-life instances using data gathered from three food banks in the Netherlands and Canada.

While this paper is motivated by a food bank setting, our problem can be generalized to other contexts and applied to both collection and distribution problems. Examples of this type of setting, featuring these three different types of uncertainty, outside of the food bank context, can be found in the retail industry (e.g., inventory-routing problems (Federgruen & Simchi-Levi, 1995)) as well as problems encountered in the healthcare sector (e.g., blood bank distribution problems (Kaya & Ozkok, 2020)).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a literature review and highlights our scientific contributions, before we formally describe the decision problem in Section 3. Section 4 presents the matheuristic that decomposes the problem to find a solution to the CVRP-SDSW. In Section 5, we present results obtained from numerical experiments on random and real-life instances. Finally, we draw some conclusions in Section 6.

2. Literature review

The CVRP-SDSW, introduced in this paper, belongs to the class of stochastic Vehicle Routing Problems (VRPs), which have attracted much attention since their introduction by Tillman (1969). In addition, the CVRP-SDSW relates to studies on food bank logistics, an area of research that has gained prominence in the past 10 years (Mahmoudi et al., 2022). The following subsections review the most relevant studies from both of these fields.

2.1. Vehicle routing under uncertainty

Considering different types of uncertainty, the CVRP-SDSW constitutes a new variant of the stochastic VRP, which has been extensively studied for decades (see the reviews of Gendreau et al. (2016) and Oyola et al. (2018)). Over time, this extensive research on the stochastic VRP has led to variants that incorporate several aspects of uncertainty.

A variant that has received much attention and that closely relates to the CVRP-SDSW, is the capacitated VRP with stochastic demand, for which customer demands only become known after the creation of the routes. In this case, the vehicle capacity may be exceeded, even if the expected demand along the route does not exceed the vehicle capacity. The scientific literature has proposed various actions to repair the solution when this type of route failure occurs. Examples of such actions are the detour-to-depot recourse policy, where the vehicle returns to the depot when capacity failure occurs in order to restore its capacity before resuming its route (Dror et al., 1989; Laporte et al., 2002; Secomandi & Margot, 2009), and the preventive return policy, where the route can be interrupted to travel to the depot to reset the capacity prior to the moment of failure, in the hope of avoiding a failure later on (Dror et al., 1993, 1989; Yang et al., 2000). Under consideration of a wide range of application contexts, the VRP with stochastic demand has been extended to incorporate a diverse set of practical requirements. Examples of extensions are the consideration of independent compartments in the vehicles (e.g., Goodson, 2015; Mendoza et al., 2010), or, as in our study, a restriction in the duration of the routes (e.g., Goodson, 2015; Mendoza et al., 2016).

In addition to the literature on stochastic demand, several studies have also considered VRPs with stochasticity in the service times (e.g., Errico et al., 2016; Lei et al., 2012). This type of uncertainty is, moreover, often combined with stochastic travel times and time window constraints, while demand is assumed to be deterministic (Li et al., 2010; Miranda & Conceição, 2016; Zhang et al., 2013). These studies generally also assume that the stochastic service and travel times are independent of customer demand.

In addition to stochastic service and travel times, some papers also account for uncertainty in the waiting time at customer locations. This is most common in VRPs with time windows, where the vehicle needs to wait if it arrives before the customer is ready to begin the service (Li et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2013). Additionally, some other ways of modeling waiting time have been proposed, e.g., where waiting times are random variables (Keskin et al., 2021) or time-dependent variables (Keskin et al., 2019). Various methodologies have proven to be effective for exactly or approximately solving stochastic VRPs, including robust optimization (Sungur et al., 2008), integer L-shaped methods (Hoogendoorn & Spliet, 2023; Laporte & Louveaux, 1993; Laporte et al., 2002) and heuristics such as swarm optimization (Marinakakis et al., 2013). See Gendreau et al. (2016) and Oyola et al. (2017) for in-depth surveys.

The most important distinction between the CVRP-SDSW and the standard stochastic VRP variants is that the CVRP-SDSW simultaneously tackles the uncertainties in multiple routing components. This combination of uncertainty in demand, service and waiting time has, to the best of our knowledge, not previously been studied. Additionally, the service and waiting times in the CVRP-SDSW depend on the size of the demand. This means that, rather than using random variables for these uncertainties as done in other research, we adopt a linear combination of the random variables for the demand.

To provide a solution to the CVRP-SDSW, we develop a matheuristic that bears similarities with the stochastic cluster-first route-second methodologies introduced by Yang et al. (2000) and Haugland et al. (2007). These authors propose algorithms for the CVRP where demand is realized *before* the routing phase (Haugland et al., 2007) and *after* the routing phase (Yang et al., 2000). Similarly, we also introduce and solve a stochastic variant of the classical two-phase heuristic of Fisher and Jaikumar (1981). The classical first-phase designs the routing districts by selecting seed points and then clustering the customers to these seeds. For this clustering problem under demand uncertainty, heuristics based on tabu search and multistart principles (Haugland et al., 2007) as well as on cost improvement of repositioning, inner-route exchanges and Or-opt principles (Yang et al., 2000) have been presented. In contrast, we formulate this clustering problem as a tractable programming problem, for which we present a linear and convex quadratic variant,

which can be solved to optimality for small instances. This programming problem is a probabilistic variant of the generalized assignment problem, which constitutes a significant methodological contribution as, to the best of our knowledge, the probabilistic variant has not yet been investigated.

2.2. Vehicle routing for food banks

Decision support models for food aid supply chains have received growing attention in recent years (Mahmoudi et al., 2022; Rivera et al., 2023). The following focuses specifically on food bank logistics, showing that the majority of studies on VRPs for food banks do not take uncertainty into account.

Gunes et al. (2010), for example, consider a deterministic pickup and delivery problem for a food rescue program where surplus food is collected from suppliers and distributed to food agencies. The combination of a deterministic VRP and resource allocation decisions has, moreover, received considerable attention in recent years (Eisenhandler & Tzur, 2019a, 2019b; Nair et al., 2018, 2016, 2017; Orgut & Lodree, 2023; Rey et al., 2018). For instance, Eisenhandler and Tzur (2019a) and Eisenhandler and Tzur (2019b) model the effective and equitable allocation of food alongside its delivery to food agencies. Another deterministic problem integrating routing with facility location decisions was studied by Solak et al. (2014) and Davis et al. (2014). Solak et al. (2014) introduced the “stop-and-drop” problem, in which food is delivered by the food bank to “drop” locations, from which agencies can in turn collect it. Their problem particularly applies to food banks in remote areas and determines the routes for the food banks, the optimal placement of these drop locations, and the matching of the agencies to the drop locations. Davis et al. (2014) study a similar problem by using a set of satellite locations as possible transshipment points between a food bank and an agency.

Despite this growing interest in VRPs for food banks, there is a notable lack of attention towards the modeling of uncertainty in this context. To the best of our knowledge, Lien et al. (2014) and Balciik et al. (2014) are the only authors who have modeled uncertainty. Lien et al. (2014) include uncertainty in the demand, considering a problem in which the order of visits to the donors and the food agencies, as well as the delivery amounts to the agencies, must be determined for a single vehicle. The demand at each node remains unknown until the arrival of the vehicle. Balciik et al. (2014) extended this problem to a multi-vehicle setting.

Table 1 provides an overview of the presented food bank papers, summarizing the types of uncertainty that have been included (column 2) and the country from which the problem or the case study originates (column 3). The table reveals that studies on VRPs for food banks taking into account uncertainty are still rare, while studies focusing on other aspects in the food bank supply chain increasingly highlight the existence and importance of uncertainty (Akkerman et al., 2023). As a result, research on food bank supply chains has started to include uncertainties, for example, in the demand for food assistance (Reusken et al., 2023), the supply of food donations (Davis et al., 2016; Paul & Davis, 2022), as well as the available capacity at food agencies (Orgut et al., 2018). Despite this increasing attention, the survey of Mahmoudi et al. (2022) confirms the observed gap, and stresses the significance of considering the multitude of uncertain factors that characterize real-life food bank settings. One goal of this research is therefore to fill this research gap by incorporating the notion of uncertainty into the context of VRPs for food banks. The inspiration for the problem, as well as the real-life data used for this research, originate from food banks in the Netherlands and Canada, two settings that have not yet been studied (see Table 1).

Table 1

Table summarizing the literature on VRPs for food banks.

	Uncertainty	Country
Gunes et al. (2010)		USA
Balciik et al. (2014)	Demand	USA
Davis et al. (2014)		USA
Lien et al. (2014)	Demand	USA
Solak et al. (2014)		USA
Nair et al. (2016)		Australia
Nair et al. (2017)		Australia
Nair et al. (2018)		Australia
Rey et al. (2018)		Australia
Eisenhandler and Tzur (2019a)		Israel and USA
Eisenhandler and Tzur (2019b)		Israel and USA
Orgut and Lodree (2023)		USA

3. Problem description

While this paper is inspired by the practical decisions faced by food banks, our problem generalizes the single-period capacitated VRP with travel time restrictions, and stochasticity in the demand, as well as in the service and waiting times at the customer locations. Incorporating both strategic and operational decisions, the overall goal of this problem is to determine a minimum number of districts (equal to the number of vehicles in our context) as well as to identify a cost-effective route for each of these districts, serving all customers. Since the strategic design of the districts significantly impacts operational decisions related to the routes, it is important to ensure that the proposed decisions are robust. We therefore prioritize this strategic aspect of the problem, generating solutions that withstand the uncertainties with a controlled probability. Based on these decisions at the strategic level, the problem then aims to generate routes that cope with uncertainty at the operational level through the use of a recourse policy. Considering the respective significance of these two decision levels, the objective of the problem is hierarchical in nature: first minimizing the number of vehicles and then the routing cost, which in our case is expressed in the form of travel time.

One of the main challenges of this problem lies in the incorporation of three sources of uncertainty. First, the demand remains unknown until the vehicle arrives at a customer location. Second, the service time is also stochastic since it is considered proportional to the demand and includes both handling activities at the customer locations as well as at the depot. Third, since vehicles may be forced to queue before servicing a customer in case no loading dock is immediately available, this waiting time is uncertain and depends on the number of vehicles in the queue. The length of the queue will only be known upon arrival, and the unit service time for the vehicles waiting in the queue is assumed to be identical for all vehicles at a given location. These time considerations are accounted for in the travel time, which encompasses the time spent on service, waiting, driving and potentially returning to the depot in order to restore capacity in case of route failure. The challenge of incorporating these uncertainty sources is further amplified by the different decision levels involved in our problem, i.e., the combination of strategic and operational decisions. A more detailed overview of these individual decisions is provided in the following.

1. **Strategic decisions.** The decisions at the strategic level all relate to the design of districts. The first decision at this level concerns the number of districts into which the service area should be divided. For each of the districts, the decision maker requires a vehicle and a driver, and all vehicles are considered to be identical. Since the team of drivers and the fleet of vehicles cannot be regularly revised, the number of districts is a decision made at the strategic level that holds highest priority. Furthermore, we consider the fixed cost associated with each driver as well as each vehicle to be substantially large, making it reasonable to assume that fewer vehicles consistently leads to lower costs.

As a result, the ideal number of districts must be as small as possible. Given the number of districts, the second strategic decision concerns the assignment of each customer to precisely one district, with the aim of minimizing the overall route cost. Both of these decisions are dependent on (i) the customer demands to satisfy the vehicle capacity, and (ii) the total travel time which should normally not exceed the maximum duration of the driver’s working day. Hence, the number of districts as well as the customer assignment to districts must be robust to this stochastic setting in which the probability of not satisfying any of these two conditions may not exceed a predetermined threshold. This guarantees that violations of the vehicle capacity and the travel time limit are infrequent occurrences.

- Operational decisions.** Compared to the strategic decisions, the decisions made at the operational level concern the more immediate and shorter-term operations planning, which can be revised more flexibly. The final decision in our problem lies at the operational level and relates to the route associated with each district, i.e., the order in which customers are visited. Each route starts and ends at the depot, which is shared among the districts. Given the demand uncertainty, higher levels than the anticipated demand can result in a route that violates the vehicle capacity, i.e., in a route failure. As in Dror et al. (1993), we assume that this can only occur at the last customer of the route. This is justified by the fact that the probability of exceeding the vehicle capacity twice on the same route is extremely small, and that if at most one failure can occur, the customer location with the highest probability of failure is the last one. One of two actions can be taken in this situation: (i) return to the depot upon failure to reset the capacity, or (ii) plan a preventive return to the depot at a suitable location earlier in the route to avoid a possibly costly failure at the last customer location (Dror et al., 1989; Dror et al., 1993).

4. Methodology

Given its stochastic nature and the fact that it combines several NP-hard subproblems, the CVRP-SDSW is highly complex and difficult to solve exactly, even for relatively small instances. Therefore, we propose a matheuristic that decomposes the problem into several natural decisions in order to find a solution. In this context, the algorithm first determines the number of districts into which the service area should be divided. In a second step, it defines these districts, using strategically selected seeds and solving a probabilistic generalized assignment problem to cluster the customers. After the creation of the districts, the matheuristic then proceeds with the route planning for each district. Periodically, the matheuristic enters an iterative procedure (IP) to verify or restore the feasibility of the solution. An overview of the structure of the algorithm is depicted in Fig. 1. The following subsections describe each step in detail.

The problem is defined over a complete directed graph $G(V, A)$, where the vertices $V = \{0\} \cup N$ represent all locations to be visited, comprising the depot location $\{0\}$ and the customer locations $N = \{1, \dots, n\}$, while $A = \{(i, j) : i, j \in V, i \neq j\}$ denotes the set of arcs.

Table 2 provides a summary of the notation used. The remaining notations in this table are explained in more detail in the subsections.

4.1. Determining the number of districts

The first step of the matheuristic is to select the initial number of districts, denoted by m . This also determines the number of vehicles and drivers, since there is exactly one vehicle per district. Given the uncertainties involved in the problem, there is a possibility that route failure may occur as a result of exceeding the vehicle capacity or the maximum travel time. As such, the choice of m should be sufficiently robust against this uncertainty inherent to the problem. We enforce

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the structure of our matheuristic. IP₁, IP₂ and IP₃ are three iterative procedures to be described in Section 4.4.

robustness by using chance constraint programming, ensuring that the probability of route failure related to the choice of m does not exceed given thresholds. For this purpose, we apply two chance constraints in order to respect the vehicle capacity and the travel time limit, determining the corresponding number of districts m^c and m^t , respectively. Considering the values of m^c and m^t , the initial number of districts m is then equal to $\max\{m^c, m^t\}$.

In terms of the vehicle capacity, this means that m^c should be set in such a way that the sum of the stochastic demands exceeds the capacity Q not more than a given proportion γ of the time i.e., m^c is the smallest integer satisfying

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\sum_{i \in N} \xi_i > m^c Q\right) \leq \gamma, \tag{1}$$

where ξ_i represents the stochastic demand of customer $i \in N$.

In addition, uncertainty may also affect the total travel time of a route, which may result in a route failure if the travel time exceeds a limit T . We consider four individual components which together determine the travel time:

- Driving.** The total duration of driving is denoted by d^v .
- Service.** The service time at a customer $i \in N$ is defined as $2a\xi_i$, where ξ_i is the demand and a is the service time per demand unit. The demand is counted twice, as vehicles need to be both loaded and unloaded. Hence, the service time includes handling at the customer location as well as at the depot location.
- Waiting.** The waiting time of a vehicle at a customer’s location $i \in N$ is considered to be dependent on the number of vehicles already in the queue, and the probability that there are h vehicles in the queue at the customer is denoted by q_{ih} . The service time for all vehicles in the queue is assumed to be identical and proportional to ξ_i , except for the first vehicle in the queue, which is expected to already be halfway through the service, so that the total service time of the h vehicles in the queue at customer i is $a(\frac{1}{2} + (h - 1))\xi_i$. The expected waiting time at customer i is then equal to $\sum_{h=1}^{\infty} q_{ih}[a(h - \frac{1}{2})\xi_i]$. The need for ξ_i arises from the lack of information about the time spent by the other vehicles in the queue, and therefore ξ_i is used as a proxy for the demand of the other vehicles assuming that this demand is similar in size across all vehicles in the queue. This is justified by the idea that large customers will for example have overall a higher level of activity.
- Recourse.** The final component that influences travel time arises from the recourse policy, which is applied whenever the realized

Table 2

Notations. We use lowercase boldface characters to denote vectors.

Sets	
N	Customers, i.e., $N = \{1, \dots, n\}$
V	Vertices, i.e., $V = \{0\} \cup N$
A	Arcs, i.e., $A = \{(i, j) : i, j \in V, i \neq j\}$
K	Districts, i.e., $K = \{1, \dots, m\}$
S_k	Customers in district $k \in K$, i.e., $S_k = \{i \in N : x_{ik} = 1\}$
D_k	Vertices in district $k \in K$ used for routing, i.e., $D_k = \{0\} \cup S_k \cup \{ S_k + 1, S_k + 2\}$
K_λ^*	Districts for which the assignment of customers to districts is infeasible at iteration λ , where $K_\lambda^* \subseteq K$
S_λ^*	Accumulated family of sets of customer groups that result in infeasible solutions at iteration λ , i.e., $S_\lambda^* = \{S_{k-1}^* \cup S_k : k \in K_\lambda^*\}$
Parameters	
γ	Safety factor for vehicle capacity to determine m^c
δ	Safety factor for travel time limit to determine m^t
α	Safety factor for vehicle capacity in assignment of customers to districts
η	Safety factor for travel time limit in assignment of customers to districts
a	Service time per demand unit
s	Driving speed
q_{ih}	Probability that h vehicles are waiting in queue at customer $i \in N$
c_{ij}	Length of arc $(i, j) \in A$
M	Arbitrarily large positive number
Q	Vehicle capacity
T	Travel time limit
λ	Iteration count
ψ	Termination scalar for the iteration count
Unknown parameters	
d_k^v	Duration of driving in district $k \in K$
d^v	Total duration of driving
d_k^r	Duration of recourse in district $k \in K$
d^r	Total duration of recourse
\bar{c}_{ik}	Distance associated with assigning customer $i \in N$ to district $k \in K$
Approximations	
\bar{c}_{ik}	Approximated distance of assigning customer $i \in N$ to district $k \in K$
\bar{d}_1	Approximation for $d^v + d^r$ used to determine the number of districts
$\bar{d}_2(x)$	Approximation for $d^v + d^r$ used in the assignment of customers to districts
Variables	
ξ_i	Random variable for stochastic demand of customer $i \in N$
x_{ik}	Decision variable for assignment of customers to districts: 1 if customer $i \in N$ is allocated to district $k \in K$, 0 otherwise
y_{ijk}	Decision variable for routing: 1 if arc $(i, j) \in D_k$ is used in district $k \in K$, 0 otherwise

demand exceeds the vehicle capacity at the last customer. To overcome this type of failure and repair the solution, we consider two possible actions. First, the vehicle may travel from the last customer to the depot to reset its capacity, before revisiting that customer. In this case, the duration of recourse d^r is equal to the expected additional duration of the round trip between the last customer and the depot. As a second option, vehicles can plan a preventive return to the depot at a suitable location (see Section 3), in which case the duration of recourse d^r is equal to zero, and the duration of driving d^v includes the driving time of the extra stop at the depot.

These four elements aggregate into the total travel time, which should not exceed the maximum time limit T with a probability of more than δ . Based on this, we formulate the following chance constraint in order to determine the appropriate number of districts, equal to the smallest integer m^t satisfying

$$\mathbb{P} \left(d^v + d^r + \sum_{i \in N} \left(2a\xi_i + \sum_{h=1}^{\infty} a(h - \frac{1}{2})q_{ih}\xi_i \right) > m^t T \right) \leq \delta. \tag{2}$$

It should be noted, in this context, that to be able to compute m^t from this constraint, the demands $(\xi_i, i \in N)$ need to be independent and follow a stable distribution (e.g., a normal or a Cauchy distribution, see Fama and Roll (1968)). In this research, we present tractable solutions and experiments for normal independently distributed demand, which is the most frequently considered demand distribution in the stochastic VRP literature (Oyola et al., 2018). From a food bank perspective, the assumption of independent demands is sensible since donors may vary significantly (e.g. supermarkets, farmers, big manufacturers), making it difficult to identify common factors affecting

the volume of food donations. Since the actual time spent on driving and recourse are not yet known at this stage of the solution procedure, we introduce \bar{d}_1 as an approximation for $d^v + d^r$.

Approximation 1. [\bar{d}_1] Due to the limited information that is available regarding the districts at this stage, we use the formula of Beardwood et al. (1959) to approximate the length of an optimal route of a Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) on the graph $G(V, A)$. Considering that time = distance/speed, the approximation for the duration is given by

$$\bar{d}_1 = \frac{\beta(n)\sqrt{E(n+1)}}{s},$$

where s denotes the speed and E is the size of the service area, estimating the constant $\beta(n)$, as in Tables 1 and 2 of Franceschetti et al. (2017).

4.2. Districting

Now that the number of districts has been determined, we assign each customer to exactly one district. This is achieved in two stages. First, a subset of customers are chosen to serve as seed points, one for each district. In the second stage, a probabilistic generalized assignment problem is solved, where, as in Fisher and Jaikumar (1981), the seeds are used to estimate the distance associated with assigning a customer to a specific district. This problem is stochastic, since demand, service and waiting times are uncertain. Solving these two stages, which are described in more detail below, provides a feasible assignment of customers for each district (or vehicle), considering the limited available information at this stage.

4.2.1. Seed selection

While several methods have been proposed for seed selection (e.g., Baker & Sheasby, 1999; Koskosidis & Powell, 1992; Sultana et al., 2017), this research applies the k-means clustering algorithm, initially proposed by Macqueen (1967). In k-means clustering, several data points are partitioned into clusters so that the within-cluster variances (squared Euclidean distances) are minimized. The method is summarized in Algorithm 1 and adapted to partition the n customers into m clusters. We adopt the common practice of repeating the entire k-means algorithm multiple times with different initial centroids and choose the clustering result that yields the lowest sum of squared distances. For this clustering result, we select for each cluster the furthest customer from the depot as the seed, following the seed selection method of Fisher and Jaikumar (1981). This composite method works well for all types of customer densities, and is also intuitive and computationally efficient.

Algorithm 1 k-means clustering

- 1: Randomly select m customers as the initial centroids
- 2: **repeat**
- 3: Assign each customer to its closest centroid to create clusters
- 4: Update centroids by taking means of customer locations within each cluster
- 5: **until**
- 6: The centroids remain unchanged

4.2.2. Assignment of customers to districts

Next, we allocate the customers to districts using a probabilistic extension of the classical Generalized Assignment Problem proposed by Fisher and Jaikumar (1981) for the deterministic case. We introduce the binary decision variables x_{ik} for the customer assignment to the districts, where $x_{ik} = 1$ if and only if customer $i \in N$ is allocated to district $k \in K$. We formulate the probabilistic generalized assignment problem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{i \in N} \bar{c}_{ik} x_{ik} & (3) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & \sum_{k \in K} x_{ik} = 1 & i \in N \quad (4) \\ & \mathbb{P} \left(\sum_{i \in N} \xi_i x_{ik} > Q \right) \leq \alpha & k \in K \quad (5) \\ & \mathbb{P} \left(d_k^v + d_k^r + \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \left(2a\xi_i + \sum_{h=1}^{\infty} a(h - \frac{1}{2})q_{ih}\xi_i \right) > T \right) \leq \eta & k \in K \quad (6) \\ & x_{ik} \in \{0, 1\} & i \in N, k \in K. \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

The objective (3) of this model is to minimize the total travel distance, where \bar{c}_{ik} denotes the distance associated with assigning customer $i \in N$ to district $k \in K$. Constraints (4) then ensure that each customer is allocated to exactly one district, while chance constraints (5) guarantee that the probability of exceeding the vehicle capacity in a district is at most α . Similarly, constraints (6) ensure that the total travel time, consisting of the driving, recourse, service and waiting time in a district, exceeds the travel time limit with a probability of at most η . Finally, constraints (7) define the domains of variables x_{ik} .

Note that in this formulation the parameters \bar{c}_{ik} , d_k^v and d_k^r are unknown. In order to estimate them we introduce an updated approximation for $d^v + d^r$.

Approximation 2. [$\bar{d}_2(x)$] At this stage of the solution procedure, new information relative to Approximation 1 becomes available, namely the number of districts as well as the seed of each district. Consequently, we propose the updated approximation

$$\bar{d}_2(x) = \sum_{k \in K} \left(\frac{c_{0jk} + c_{jk0}}{s} + \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \frac{\bar{c}_{ik}}{s} \right),$$

where x is the vector of variables x_{ik} , $i \in N$, $k \in K$ and \bar{c}_{ik} denotes the approximate distance of assigning customer $i \in N$ to district $k \in K$. This distance corresponds to the increase in distance associated with inserting customer $i \in N$ in a route that starts and ends at the depot and visits the seed in district $k \in K$. Since \bar{c}_{ik} includes only the increase in distance of inserting a customer, the round trip between the seed and the depot is separately added in $\bar{d}_2(x)$ using c_{0jk} , which denotes the distance from the depot to the seed customer j_k of district $k \in K$.

Using this estimate the objective in (3) can be approximated using

$$\min \bar{d}_2(x), \tag{8}$$

which provides a solution that is equivalent to minimizing (i) the approximate total travel distance (i.e., $\sum_{k \in K} \sum_{i \in N} \bar{c}_{ik} x_{ik}$) and (ii) the approximate total travel time (i.e., adding the expected service and waiting time to $\bar{d}_2(x)$). These formulations are identical in terms of the optimal assignment since all components, except $\bar{c}_{ik} x_{ik}$, are constants that are independent of the assignment.

In addition to the objective, constraints (6) can be approximated using the expression $\bar{d}_2(x)$, which gives for $k \in K$

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\frac{c_{0jk} + c_{jk0}}{s} + \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \left(\frac{\bar{c}_{ik}}{s} + 2a\xi_i + \sum_{h=1}^{\infty} a(h - \frac{1}{2})q_{ih}\xi_i \right) > T \right) \leq \eta. \tag{9}$$

In summary, the approximated model, consisting of (4), (5), (7), (8) and (9), establishes the assignment of customers to districts. In order to solve this model, we introduce a tractable reformulation of the probabilistic constraints (5) and (9). In the following, a convex quadratic and a linear reformulation are presented. One can implement the assignment problem by choosing one of these reformulations, or alternatively by using another reformulation that is computationally tractable.

Convex quadratic reformulation

Since the random variables ξ_i , $i \in N$ are assumed to be mutually independent and to follow normal distributions with means μ_i , $i \in N$ and variances σ_i^2 , $i \in N$, we can reformulate constraints (5) by exploiting the property that normal distributions are invariant under addition (Fama & Roll, 1968). Hence, $\sum_{i \in N} \xi_i x_{ik}$ follows the same distribution as ξ_i , with mean $\sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik}$ and variance $\sum_{i \in N} \sigma_i^2 x_{ik}^2$. Constraints (5), therefore, allow the following reformulation

$$\sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik} + F^{-1}(1 - \alpha) \sqrt{\sum_{i \in N} \sigma_i^2 x_{ik}^2} \leq Q \quad k \in K, \tag{10}$$

where $F^{-1}(\cdot)$ denotes the inverse cumulative distribution function of ξ_i (also frequently named the quantile or percent-point function). Inequalities (10) hold if the following constraints are satisfied for $k \in K$:

$$(F^{-1}(1 - \alpha))^2 \sum_{i \in N} \sigma_i^2 x_{ik} + 2Q \sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik} - \left(\sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik} \right)^2 \leq Q^2 \tag{11}$$

$$Q - \sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik} \geq 0. \tag{12}$$

Note that these inequalities exploit the property that x_{ik} is binary, i.e., that $x_{ik}^2 = x_{ik}$, $i \in N$, $k \in K$. Inequalities (11) then follow directly from squaring both sides of constraints (10). This operation is paired with the requirements of $Q - \sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik}$ and $F^{-1}(1 - \alpha) \sqrt{\sum_{i \in N} \sigma_i^2 x_{ik}^2}$ being nonnegative. The first requirement is enforced by constraints (12), and the second requirement holds trivially, since the components themselves are nonnegative.

A tractable convex quadratic reformulation of constraints (9) can be derived equivalently (see Appendix A).

Linear reformulation

The nonlinearity arising in the term $(\sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik})^2$ of constraints (11) can, moreover, also be linearized. First, note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i \in N} \mu_i^2 x_{ik}^2 + 2 \sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \neq i, j \in N} \mu_i \mu_j x_{ik} x_{jk} \\ &= \sum_{i \in N} \mu_i^2 x_{ik} + 2 \sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \neq i, j \in N} \mu_i \mu_j x_{ik} x_{jk}, \end{aligned}$$

since x_{ik} is binary. By introducing the new variables z_{ijk} , $i \in N$, $j > i$, $j \in N$, $k \in K$, inequalities (11) can be replaced with the following linear constraints in x_{ik} and z_{ijk} :

$$\begin{aligned} & (F^{-1}(1-\alpha))^2 \sum_{i \in N} \sigma_i^2 x_{ik} + 2Q \sum_{i \in N} \mu_i x_{ik} - \sum_{i \in N} \mu_i^2 x_{ik} \\ & - 2 \sum_{i \in N} \sum_{j \neq i, j \in N} \mu_i \mu_j z_{ijk} \leq Q^2 \quad k \in K \\ z_{ijk} & \geq x_{ik} + x_{jk} - 1 \quad i \in N, j > i, j \in N, k \in K \\ z_{ijk} & \leq x_{ik} \quad i \in N, j > i, j \in N, k \in K \\ z_{ijk} & \leq x_{jk} \quad i \in N, j > i, j \in N, k \in K. \end{aligned}$$

4.3. Routing

After determining the assignment of customers to districts, we need to solve a stochastic TSP for each district. Since we consider a setting where (i) route failure may only occur at the last customer's location and (ii) a preventive return to the depot may be scheduled in the hope of avoiding a costlier return at a later stage, the transformation of Dror et al. (1993) can be applied. This transformation reduces our stochastic TSP to a deterministic TSP, by building on the following ideas. First, only one of the two cases (i) and (ii) can occur. Second, the probability of route failure in district k is equal to

$$p_k = \mathbb{P} \left(\sum_{i \in S_k} \xi_i > Q \right) \quad k \in K,$$

where S_k denotes the customers in district k , i.e., $S_k = \{i \in N : x_{ik} = 1\}$. Note that $p_k \leq \alpha$ for all k . Based on this setting, two artificial vertices $|S_k| + 1$ and $|S_k| + 2$ are introduced for each district k . Entering $|S_k| + 1$ from customer i indicates a preventive route break, and entering $|S_k| + 2$ from customer i indicates that route failure may occur at a cost of $p_k(c_{i0} + c_{0i})$. One of these two vertices is visited, which is imposed by setting $c_{|S_k|+1, |S_k|+2}$ and $c_{|S_k|+2, |S_k|+1}$, $k \in K$, equal to $-M$, where M is an arbitrarily large positive number. For an explanation of the other c_{ij} associated with the artificial vertices and a detailed description of the transformation, we refer to Dror et al. (1993), pp. 280–281.

Considering the original vertices of a district together with the newly introduced artificial ones, we obtain the sets $D_k = \{0\} \cup S_k \cup \{|S_k| + 1, |S_k| + 2\}$, $k \in K$. Using the Dror et al. (1993) transformation of the distance matrix, the routes can now be determined by solving m TSPs, i.e., one for every vertex set D_k . By determining these routes, we obtain the expected duration of driving and recourse, i.e., the routing solutions for $k \in K$ are

$$\begin{aligned} d_k^r &= \begin{cases} \frac{p_k(c_{i0} + c_{0i})}{s} & \text{if route failure is risked} \\ & \text{at the last visited customer } i \text{ in district } k \\ 0 & \text{if a preventive return to the depot} \\ & \text{is scheduled in district } k \end{cases} \quad (13) \\ d_k^v &= \frac{\sum_{(i,j) \in D_k} c_{ij} y_{ijk} + M}{s}, \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

where y_{ijk} is a binary variable equal to 1 if and only if arc $(i, j) \in D_k$ is used in the TSP solution in district k . Note that the travel time of the extra trip to the depot, resulting from the recourse action of scheduling a preventive return to the depot, is included in the driving time d_k^v . The expected duration of driving and recourse of the combined districts is

then equal to

$$d^r = \sum_{k \in K} d_k^r \quad (15)$$

$$d^v = \sum_{k \in K} d_k^v. \quad (16)$$

A feasible solution to the CVRP-SDSW is obtained when the time chance constraints used to determine the number of districts (constraint (2)) and the assignment of customers to districts (constraints (6)) are satisfied for these routing solutions.

4.4. Iterative procedures to achieve feasibility

The last feature of the matheuristic lies in the iterative procedures IP₁, IP₂ and IP₃, shown in Fig. 1. These procedures aim to regain feasibility when an infeasible solution is encountered. It may happen, however, that even after several iterations no feasible solution can be identified. This can be for one of two reasons: (i) the approximation $\tilde{d}_2(x)$ used in the assignment of customers to districts is inaccurate for a certain instance and prevents the matheuristic from finding a feasible solution, or (ii) the uncertainty inherent to the problem yields infeasible solutions. In the case of these rare events, two stopping criteria are considered for the algorithm. First, the number of iterations is limited to at most $\psi|K|$, where ψ should be large enough to evaluate an adequate number of solutions. This limit depends on $|K|$, since larger instances are likely to require more iterations in order to reach feasibility. A second stopping criterion is a runtime limit, which is checked before proceeding to another iteration. As long as these limits are not reached, the iterative procedures continue the search for a feasible solution. More precisely, these procedures activate the following actions.

IP₁: **Increase m when the assignment of customers to districts is infeasible.** The number of districts is increased to $m + 1$, when the assignment of customers to districts is infeasible.

IP₂: **Decrease m when it has been incorrectly initialized.** The number of districts is decreased to $m - 1$ when the approximation \tilde{d}_1 resulted in initializing too many districts. Specifically, we test the feasibility of constraint (2), while adopting the routing solution $d^v + d^r$ (obtained from (15) and (16)). If this results in a reduction in the value of m , the iterative procedure IP₂ returns to the districting subproblem with $m - 1$. Given that IP₁ yields the opposite output, i.e., iterating while considering $m + 1$, the tested values of m are stored in order to consider each value at most once. Note that iterating for this reason will rarely happen, since the following scenarios would have to occur simultaneously: (i) the travel time limit is more constraining than the vehicle capacity, i.e., $m^c \leq m^t$, and (ii) the adjustment in m^t results in a lower integer value.

IP₃: **Exclusion of infeasible customer combinations when the time chance constraints (6) are violated.** Infeasible customer combinations are excluded from forming districts in subsequent iterations of the assignment problem when the time chance constraints (6) are violated while considering the routing solutions $d_k^v + d_k^r$, $k \in K$ obtained from (13) and (14). If a district is in violation at iteration λ , it is then added to the set of infeasible districts K_λ^* , where $K_\lambda^* \subseteq K$. Across iterations, we keep track of the customers belonging to these infeasible districts, using the accumulated family of sets at iteration λ , denoted by $S_\lambda^* = \{S_{\lambda-1}^* \cup S_k^* : k \in K_\lambda^*\}$, where $S_k = \{i \in N : x_{ik} = 1\}$ denotes the customers in district $k \in K$. As such, the assignment problem (presented in Section 4.2.2) at iteration $\lambda + 1$ is augmented with the following constraints:

$$\sum_{i \in B} x_{ik} \leq |B| - 1 \quad k \in K, B \in S_\lambda^*. \quad (17)$$

Fig. 2. Depot and customer locations in instances c101, c201 and r101. The square depicts the depot, whereas the points correspond to customers, with the lighter colored points corresponding to the first 20 customers.

5. Numerical analysis

The proposed matheuristic was coded in Python 3.10.5 using `scikit-learn` 1.0.2 for seed selection, Gurobi 9.5.2 for the assignment of customers to districts, and `python-tsp` 0.3.1 for the route planning of each district. For reasons of transparency and generalizability, the data and code used have been made accessible on the Github page of the first author (Reusken, 2023). A number of computational experiments were carried out to assess the performance of the matheuristic. All computations were executed on the same machine equipped with two Intel®Xeon®Platinum 8268 processors (2.9 GHz base clock), and a limit of 128 GB of RAM on each processor. In the following, we first describe the instances and inputs that have been used to test the matheuristic, before providing an analysis of the numerical results from the experiments.

5.1. Description of the instances

The analysis was performed using a randomly generated data set, inspired by the instances proposed by Solomon (1987), and several real-life data sets, originating from food banks in the Netherlands and Canada.

5.1.1. Random instances

The random instances used for our experiments originate from the well-known benchmark instances created by Solomon (1987). These instances consider three types of geographical distributions of the customer locations: clustered (C), random (R) and a mixture of random and clustered (RC). For the main analysis in this research, we selected the first data sets of types C and R with unique customer locations, i.e., data sets c101, c201 and r101. We created subsets to increase the number and variety of instances by extracting the first 20 to 100 customer locations from these data sets, with intervals of 10, resulting in a total of 27 instances. The travel distance (c_{ij}) between the locations is computed based on the Euclidean distance. Fig. 2 provides a graphical representation of the three data sets, showing the distribution of customers over the service region. Depicting the first 20 customers in lighter color, this graphical representation also illustrates the impact on the spread of customers within the service region when using only a small subset of the customer locations.

In addition to the customer and depot locations, we also used the same vehicle capacity (Q) and customer demands as in Solomon (1987). Because the customer demands in these instances are deterministic, we used them as a mean (μ_i , $i \in N$) for the stochastic demands in our problem, which we assume to be normally distributed with a standard deviation of $\sigma_i = 0.2\mu_i$, $i \in N$. Moreover, since we assume uncertain waiting times, we generated for each customer $i \in N$ a sensible probability q_{ih} of having h vehicles waiting in the queue. For this purpose, we assume that (i) q_{ih} varies across customers, and (ii) q_{ih}

Table 3

Parameter settings.

Parameter	Value
T Travel time limit	8
s Driving speed (km/h)	50
γ Safety factor for vehicle capacity to determine m'	0.01
δ Safety factor for travel time limit to determine m'	0.01
α Safety factor for vehicle capacity in assignment of customers to districts	0.05
η Safety factor for travel time limit in assignment of customers to districts	0.05
a Service time per demand unit	0.008

is likely to decrease with higher values of h . The precise steps taken to generate the values for q_{ih} can be found in Appendix B.1.

Finally, the remaining input parameters are location-independent and were set to realistic values, summarized in Table 3. In this context, the travel time limit T , corresponding to a workday of a driver, is set to eight hours, and the average speed of the trucks is assumed to be 50 km/h. Moreover, since in a practical setting the number of districts, and therefore the number of vehicles, cannot be modified on a daily basis, we only allow for a 1% probability of failure to meet the vehicle capacity and travel time limit when determining the number of districts, i.e., $\gamma = 0.01$ and $\delta = 0.01$. In contrast, the safety factors for meeting the vehicle capacity (α) and travel time limit (η) in the assignment problem are set more leniently (to values of 0.05), since a route can be changed more easily than the number of vehicles. Furthermore, given that the mean values of the customer demands are between one and 50 for our instances, we consider a service time a per demand unit of 0.008 h, which corresponds to approximately five minutes per 10 demand units.

5.1.2. Real-life instances

In order to highlight the practical relevance of our matheuristic, we also applied our method to a number of real-life instances, resulting from in-depth field work conducted at a total of six food banks in the Netherlands and Canada (Food Bank Zevenaar,¹ Food Bank Eemsdelta,² Food Bank Haaglanden,³ Food Bank Almelo,⁴ Moisson Montréal,⁵ and Share the Warmth⁶). This field work involved several interviews with operational and managerial staff, inspections of equipment and facilities, as well as accompanying a driver during a normal operating day on his collection route. The results of this practical study showed that all of these food banks face a similar collection problem, experiencing high

¹ See <https://www.voedselbankzevenaar.nl/> (in Dutch)

² See <https://www.voedselbankeemsdelta.nl/> (in Dutch)

³ See <https://voedselbankhaaglanden.nl/> (in Dutch)

⁴ See <https://www.voedselbankalmelo.nl/> (in Dutch)

⁵ See <https://www.moissonmontreal.org/en/>

⁶ See <https://sharethewarmth.ca/>

Table 4
Summary of the real-life data sets.

1. Organization name	Food Bank Zevenaar	Food Bank Eemsdelta	Moisson Montréal
2. Country	The Netherlands	The Netherlands	Canada
3. Organization type	Food agency	Food agency	Food bank depot
4. Number of instances	1	2	6
5. Number of collection locations	7	17	252
6. Collection area in km ²	257	773	403
7. Vehicle capacity in kg (Q)	2500	1000	4535
8. Travel time limit in hours (T)	4	4	8
9. Range of historic collection demands in kg	–	[2, 64]	[5, 1241]
10. Service time in hours per kg (a)	0.008	0.008	0.0008

levels of uncertainty in the collection demands, which also affect service and waiting times. Unfortunately only three of the food banks were able to provide sufficient data to generate instances corresponding to the real-life cases, namely Food Bank Zevenaar, Food Bank Eemsdelta and Moisson Montréal.

The data provided by these food banks are summarized in Table 4. The first two rows present the organization's name and the country in which it is based. The third row indicates the role of the organization in the food bank supply chain, where a *food agency* provides food assistance to the community in need, and a *food bank depot* supplies food to such food agencies. Consequently, these two organization types typically work with different types of collection locations, i.e., the food agency collects small demands from suppliers in its proximity (e.g. local bakeries) as well as from its supplying food bank depot, while the food bank depot generally collects larger demands from a larger geographical area. Row 4 presents the number of instances that are available for each organization, which corresponds to different sets of collection locations that had to be visited in a given week for the Dutch food agencies, and on each day of the week for Moisson Montréal. Row 5 shows the total number of collection locations. A subset of these locations, along with the depot locations, are mapped in Fig. 3 for illustrative purposes. The travel distance c_{ij} between these collection locations is computed based on the geodesic distance, i.e., the length of the shortest path between two points on Earth. The collection area (the circumscribed rectangle encompassing all nodes) is given in square kilometers in row 6 as an indication of the travel distances. The real vehicle capacities in kilograms and the daily travel time limit, corresponding to a workday of a driver, are presented in rows 7 and 8, respectively. Row 9 contains the minimum and maximum values of the historical collection demands (see Appendix B.2 for visualizations of these demands), and we adopt the ranges of Food Bank Eemsdelta for Food Bank Zevenaar as a reference for experimental purposes. The last row of the table displays the service time per demand unit, i.e., the time (in hours) required to collect a kilogram of demand. For the Dutch food agencies, where the collection demands range between two and 64 kg for our instances, we use $a = 0.008$, which corresponds to approximately five minutes per 10 kg. This value is significantly lower for the case of Moisson Montréal (i.e., $a = 0.0008$), as a food bank depot operates with a higher efficiency, processing larger quantities within a shorter duration (equivalent to approximately 100 kg per five minutes).

Considering the historical demands of Food Bank Eemsdelta and Moisson Montréal (see Appendix B.2), we can state that demands do not conform to any established classical distribution, although a vague resemblance to a normal distribution can be observed. For the purpose of computational testing we hence assume demand to be normally distributed using a mean (μ_i , $i \in N$) that is randomly sampled from the historic demand ranges indicated in Table 4, and a standard deviation of $\sigma_i = 0.2\mu_i$, $i \in N$. Moreover, since we assume uncertain waiting times, yet no historical data were available on this, we generate sensible values for parameter q_{ih} using the procedure described in Section 5.1.1 (for a detailed description, we refer readers to Appendix B.1). Finally, the values of s , γ , δ , α and η are set to the same realistic values as in the case of the random instances (see Table 3).

5.2. Preliminary experiments on training instances

To tune the performance of our matheuristic, a series of preliminary experiments were carried out using random instances that we did not use for our main experiments. Specifically, we used the locations, vehicle capacity and demands of the first RC data set by Solomon (1987), i.e., data set rc101. We generated subsets of sizes $\{20, 30, \dots, 100\}$, ensuring that each subset consisted of an equal proportion of customers from both the random and clustered groups. The results of these experiments determined which assignment problem reformulation to use, as well as the setup of an efficient procedure reducing the number of variables in the assignment problem, and finally the stopping criteria for our matheuristic.

5.2.1. Reformulation of the assignment problem

In Section 4.2.2, we present two computationally tractable reformulations of the assignment problem, a linear and a convex quadratic one. Preliminary experiments showed that the performances of these reformulations are comparable in terms of computational time. However, given the large number of additional variables required for the linear reformulation, we have selected the convex quadratic reformulation for our numerical analysis.

5.2.2. Reduction of the number of variables for the assignment problem

Preliminary experiments have shown that most of the computational time is spent on the assignment of customers to districts, as solving this subproblem can take up to several hours depending on the size of the instance. Computational experiments have furthermore indicated that reducing the number of decision variables x_{ik} , determining the assignment of customer i to a seed in district k , can significantly reduce computational times without considerably affecting the solution quality. For this purpose, we set the decision variables x_{ik} that correspond to the seeds furthest away from a customer equal to zero, by adding the following constraints to the assignment problem:

$$x_{ik} = 0 \quad k \in F_i, i \in N, \quad (18)$$

where $F_i = \{1, \dots, \kappa\}$ denotes the set of seeds that are furthest away from customer $i \in N$, with $F_i \subseteq K$. These κ seeds correspond to those that contain the largest insertion costs \tilde{c}_{ik} .

Several values for κ were tested, and the best performance was observed for $\kappa = \lfloor 0.3|K| \rfloor$. It should be noted that we only adopt this procedure of reducing the number of variables for those instances with $|N| \geq 60$, since the reduction in computational time for small instances is limited, and the additional constraints may very rarely cause the assignment of customers to districts to be infeasible for small instances.

5.2.3. Stopping criteria

The wall clock time limit for the matheuristic is set to 7,200 s, and the termination scalar is set to $\psi = 10$, so that the maximum iteration count is limited to $10|K|$. These stopping criteria will only terminate the procedure between iterations, so that an iteration is never interrupted. In addition, since the assignment of customers to districts can be very time consuming for larger instances, several specific stopping criteria

Fig. 3. Depot and customer locations from one instance of Food Bank Zevenaar, two instances of Food Bank Eemsdelta, and two instances of Moisson Montréal. The square depicts the depot, and the round points represent the sets of collection locations.

Table 5

Results of the matheuristic on the random instances. The four components of duration are abbreviated using ‘V’ for driving, ‘W’ for waiting, ‘S’ for service and ‘R’ for recourse.

Instance	Districts		Duration					# of IP	Time (s)			
	Data set	N	K	Average (h)	V (%)	W (%)	S (%)		R (%)	IP ₁	Assignment	Routing
c101	20	3	3.4	39	5	56	0.4	0	1	1	1	2
	30	3	4.6	33	6	60	0.3	0	1	1	1	2
	40	5	4.2	39	6	55	0.3	1	3649	1	3651	
	50	5	4.7	35	6	58	0.3	0	28	2	31	
	60	7	4.4	39	5	56	0.2	1	3643	1	3645	
	70	8	4.6	40	5	55	0.3	1	4349	23	4373	
	80	9	4.5	39	6	56	0.1	1	3952	2	3956	
	90	10	4.6	39	6	55	0.2	1	4385	6	4392	
	100	11	4.7	39	5	56	0.2	1	7267	3	7271	
	c201	20	2	5.1	39	5	57	0.0	0	0	8	9
30		3	4.9	38	6	57	0.0	1	0	10	11	
40		3	6.8	37	6	57	0.0	0	11	28	39	
50		4	5.9	36	6	58	0.0	1	510	33	544	
60		5	5.8	34	5	60	0.0	1	1164	38	1202	
70		6	5.8	37	6	57	0.0	1	4024	94	4119	
80		6	6.5	35	6	59	0.0	1	1235	71	1307	
90		7	6.3	35	6	59	0.0	1	3640	47	3687	
100		7	6.8	34	5	61	0.0	1	1738	140	1878	
r101		20	2	5.2	55	4	41	0.0	0	0	2	2
	30	3	4.9	51	4	45	0.0	0	0	2	3	
	40	4	5.0	49	6	45	0.0	0	1	4	5	
	50	4	6.0	47	5	48	0.3	0	575	19	594	
	60	5	5.5	46	5	48	0.2	0	713	21	735	
	70	6	5.3	44	5	50	0.1	0	9	16	26	
	80	7	5.1	44	5	51	0.2	0	22	22	44	
	90	8	5.1	42	6	52	0.2	0	229	12	241	
	100	9	4.9	42	5	53	0.2	1	4315	20	4337	

are applied to this subproblem, in order to allow for at least a small number of iterations within the overall time limit of two hours. As a result, the execution of the assignment problem is terminated if one of the following criteria has been met: (i) no feasible solution has been found within a wall clock time limit of 3,600 s; (ii) no improved solution has been found for eight consecutive minutes; and (iii) for instances consisting of at least 60 customers, an optimality gap of at most 5% is reached. It should be noted that the first rule activates IP₁, while the latter two rules will let the matheuristic proceed to the next step in the matheuristic.

5.3. Results on the random instances: Matheuristic performance

Using the random instances and parameter settings described in Sections 5.2 and 5.1.1, this section presents the results with regards to the performance of our matheuristic. Table 5 contains, in this context, in column 1 (Data set) and column 2 (|N|), information regarding the considered instance, i.e., the data set and the number of customers. Column 3 (|K|) provides the number of districts found by the first step of the matheuristic. In addition, information about the expected travel times of the routing solution is provided in columns 4–8. More specifically, column 4 (Average (h)) shows the average duration in hours, whereas column 5 (V (%)), column 6 (W (%)), column 7 (S (%)) and column 8 (R (%)) present the percentage of time spent on the individual components of driving, waiting, service and recourse, respectively. Focusing on the iterative procedures, column 9 (IP₁) shows the iteration count for IP₁ that were needed to obtain the presented solution (no iterations in IP₂ and IP₃ were carried out). Finally, columns 10–12 give information regarding the wall clock time in seconds, where column 10 (Assignment) presents the time spent on the assignment of customers to districts, column 11 (Routing) shows the time spent on generating routes for each district, and column 12 (Total) presents the total runtime.

The results of our experiments show that the matheuristic is able to find a feasible solution to the CVRP-SDSW for all instances presented in Table 5, including the larger instances with up to 100 customers. In all cases, the matheuristic is able to identify these solutions either

without initiating an iterative procedure or after only one IP iteration, and thus easily transforms an infeasible solution into a feasible one. The observation that no application of the iterative procedure IP₂ is ever necessary implies, moreover, that the initial number of districts is never overestimated. However, it is sometimes underestimated, as can be observed from the statistics related to the iterative procedure IP₁, which increases the number of districts after the assignment of customers to districts has been found to be infeasible. Similar to IP₂, the iterative procedure IP₃ is never applied. This indicates that Approximation 2, employed for estimating the duration of driving and recourse in the assignment problem, is a reliable approximation that consistently avoids underestimation.

Looking at the solutions themselves in more detail, we observe that the number of districts generally increases with the number of customers, while the expected duration of the routes lies on average between 3.4 and 6.8 hours, with the largest proportion of the time spent on driving and service. On average, only <1% of the time is spent on recourse, and this duration arises exclusively from risking a route failure at the last customer location of a route. This recourse action has been identified as the best strategy for all districts, and is thus more cost-effective than the other recourse action that consists of performing a preventive return to the depot.

In terms of runtime, we can see that in most cases the assignment problem accounts for the largest part of the total runtime, which tends to increase with the instance size. Furthermore, we observe differences in the runtimes of the considered data sets. For example, the r101 instances have on average significantly shorter runtimes than the instances of the other data sets. This can be explained by the even spread of customers over the service region, making the assignment of customers to districts easier, and therefore quicker to solve.

Solving the CVRP-SDSW is highly complex because of the multiple sources of uncertainty inherent to the problem. In this respect, our matheuristic ensures that the probability of route failure remains within the prescribed thresholds, in terms of vehicle capacity or travel time limit. To further analyze the presence of uncertainty within these ranges, Fig. 4 depicts a heatmap where the residual risk of failure is shown in different color shades. This heatmap presents, for every

Fig. 4. Heatmap indicating the uncertainty in the solution for the random instances, with regards to meeting the vehicle capacity (constraints (1) and (5)) and the travel time limit (constraints (2) and (6)).

instance, the sensitivity of the solution with respect to constraints (1), (2), (5) and (6). For example, for constraint (1) we use the solution found by the matheuristic for the number of districts m to compute $\mathbb{P}(\sum_{i \in N} \xi_i > mQ)$, and then depict this probability in such a way that the darkest shade corresponds to a risk of failure equal to the predetermined safety factor γ , and the lightest shade to zero risk of failure. Recall that constraints (1) and (2) are used for determining the number of districts and control for route failure when considering all districts together. Constraints (5) and (6), which are used for the assignment of customers to districts, apply to the same respective types of failure, but for each district individually.

The analysis of the uncertainty results in Fig. 4 reveals several key findings. First, we observe only the lightest shades for constraints (1) and (2), indicating that the probability of route failure, when considering all districts together, is always far below the acceptable threshold. In comparison, the uncertainty is typically higher when considering the districts individually, since we observe mostly darker shades for constraints (5) and (6). The presence of a bottleneck is, moreover, consistently limited to a single factor, i.e., the vehicle capacity or the travel time limit. Furthermore, the observed level of uncertainty exhibits differences across the data sets, where the largest uncertainties are observed for data set r101, and the smallest ones are observed for data set c201. We do not observe a clear pattern regarding the relationship with the instance size.

5.4. Results on the real-life instances: Practical implications for food banks

Given that the motivation for the CVRP-SDSW is drawn from the context of food bank operations, this section aims to derive practical insights by applying our matheuristic to this setting. To this end, we use the real-life instances described in Section 5.1.2, presenting the main results and uncertainty results in Table 6 and Fig. 5, respectively. This table and figure adhere to the same column format and layout as in Table 5 and Fig. 4. To avoid repetitions, we direct readers to the descriptions provided in Section 5.3. All presented results make use of the recourse action of risking a route failure at the last customer.

The results presented in Table 6 show that the operations of Food Bank Zevenaar and Food Bank Eemsdelta require only two routes. This is a reduction in comparison to their current scheduling which involves

four routes. Therefore, implementing the routes identified through our matheuristic is expected to result in considerable cost savings for these two food banks. Conversely, the findings reveal that Moisson Montréal, which currently employs a fleet of seven vehicles, is faced with a shortage in two particular instances. In their current planning, they often cannot serve all customers, and they occasionally violate the time limit constraint. Hence, two additional vehicles are required to collect all food donations within the time limit of eight hours, with sufficient robustness. Considering this, as well as the insights derived from Fig. 5, which reveals the travel time as the bottleneck rather than the vehicle capacity, our recommendation to Moisson Montréal is to consider expanding the number of vehicles, while reducing the vehicle capacity.

Upon examining the duration results in Table 6, we see, moreover, that the expected average duration for the instances of Food Bank Zevenaar and Food Bank Eemsdelta ranges from two to three hours, while for Moisson Montréal, the duration extends to something between six and seven hours. Given that the travel time limit for Food Bank Zevenaar and Food Bank Eemsdelta is set to four hours and for Moisson Montréal to eight hours, we can deduce that it is recommended to employ a minimum of one hour to account for the uncertainties inherent to the problem. Looking more closely at the individual travel time components, we observe that a substantial proportion of 56% to 84% of the time is expected to be spent on service activities. Since the travel time limit has been identified as the bottleneck (see Fig. 5), it is advisable to focus on enhancing the efficiency of their service operations to achieve a reduction in the overall operating time. While the results indicate that the matheuristic is able to support decision making at the food banks, reaching fast, more efficient and robust solutions, it is furthermore recommended to review the obtained solutions on a periodic basis to account for possible changes in the data.

5.5. Sensitivity results: Effects of demand uncertainty

The level of uncertainty is highly application-dependent, and therefore our next experiment is aimed at analyzing the effect of uncertainty on the performance of the matheuristic. For the standard deviation of the demand, we compare the scenarios of $\sigma = 0.1\mu$ and $\sigma = 0.3\mu$ to the base case of $\sigma = 0.2\mu$, which is given in Tables 5 and 6. We additionally

Table 6

Results of the matheuristic on real-life instances. The four components of duration are abbreviated using ‘V’ for driving, ‘W’ for waiting, ‘S’ for service and ‘R’ for recourse. Note that the travel time limit for Food Bank Zevenaar and Food Bank Eemsdelta is four hours, while for Moisson Montréal this limit is eight hours (see Table 4).

Instance	Districts		Duration					# of IP	Time (s)		
	$ N $	$ K $	Average (h)	V (%)	W (%)	S (%)	R (%)		IP ₁	Assignment	Routing
Food Bank Zevenaar	7	2	2.2	19	10	71	0.00	0	0	0	0
Food Bank Eemsdelta	8	2	2.1	36	7	56	0.00	0	0	0	0
	9	2	2.8	15	9	77	0.00	0	0	0	1
	34	7	6.0	10	9	82	0.00	1	3635	0	3636
Moisson Montréal	41	7	6.8	8	9	83	0.01	0	1046	1	1047
	42	9	6.2	9	9	82	0.01	1	4638	0	4640
	43	7	6.4	9	7	84	0.01	1	4312	0	4314
	46	9	6.7	10	9	81	0.01	1	7229	0	7230
	46	7	6.8	10	10	80	0.01	0	1347	1	1348

Fig. 5. Heatmap indicating the uncertainty in the solution for the real-life instances, with regards to meeting the vehicle capacity (constraints (1) and (5)) and the travel time limit (constraints (2) and (6)).

compare these stochastic scenarios to the deterministic version of the problem ($\sigma = 0$). We present the results of this sensitivity analysis on the random instances in Table 7 and on the real-life instances in Table 8. These tables are identically structured. The first two columns provide information on the instance where column 1 (Data set) presents the data set and column 2 ($|N|$) shows the number of customers. The subsequent four table sections contain the results for the different σ -scenarios. For each of these scenarios, we first present two statistics found by the matheuristic, namely the number of districts (see columns $|K|$), and the expected average travel time in hours (see columns Duration). The number of iterations in the iterative procedures is given (see columns IP), along with the running time in seconds in terms of wall clock time (see columns Time). For ease of comparison, the last three rows present the cumulative of the individual columns, in absolute values as well as in percentage of the base case results and of the deterministic case results.

In line with the findings observed in the base case, the matheuristic once again demonstrated its capacity to find feasible solutions, also in the scenarios of $\sigma = 0$, $\sigma = 0.1\mu$ and $\sigma = 0.3\mu$. The impact of demand uncertainty on determining the number of districts is notably evident, as our findings consistently indicate that higher levels of uncertainty lead to opting for a higher number of districts. Upon comparing the average route duration across different levels of uncertainty, a general trend emerges where the duration tends to decrease when there is more uncertainty. This trend is attributed to the incorporation of larger safety buffers in response to more uncertainty. However, it is worth noting that this pattern does not always hold true as for few instances, e.g., random instance r101, $|N| = 60$, we observe that the average duration increases with the standard deviation. This observation may be explained by the use of an approximation for the assignment problem or by the increased duration of recourse following from the formation of districts.

In addition, we observe a positive relationship between demand uncertainty and the number of iterations performed, as well as the corresponding running time. In other words, the matheuristic is generally able to find solutions more quickly, in terms of both iterations and run time, when demand is less uncertain. When there is no uncertainty at

all, solving all random instances requires only 36% of the iterations needed for the base case and 4% of the computing time.

Comparing the results of our stochastic instances with the deterministic benchmark, we observe even for the most uncertain scenarios, only a modest increase in the number of districts and a modest decrease in route duration. This indicates that the CVRP-SDSW yields feasible solutions that do not deviate significantly from their deterministic counterparts in terms of solutions, and that our matheuristic proves effective in finding these solutions. A larger difference occurs in terms of the number of iterations and the computing time. For the random instances, the number of iterations increases by a factor of three, and the computing time increases by a factor of approximately 30.

Considering the applicability of these findings, we observe that results for Food Bank Zevenaar and Food Bank Eemsdelta remain unaffected by variations in uncertainty. This robustness to changes in uncertainty can be attributed to the small sizes of these instances, resulting in simpler problem structures. This observation aligns with the results obtained from the smallest random instances in data sets c201 and r101 (see $|N| = 20$ and $|N| = 30$). The results for the larger-size instances of Moisson Montréal, in contrast, do exhibit dependencies on demand uncertainty. More specifically, we observe that lower demand uncertainty leads to selecting a smaller number of districts, vehicles, and drivers. This finding underscores the potential for cost savings, as a reduction in the number of vehicles and drivers can be achieved by predicting the collection amounts more accurately.

6. Conclusion

We have introduced the Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem with Stochastic Demand, Service and Waiting times (CVRP-SDSW). This problem finds application in many practical routing contexts, but in this paper it is motivated by the collection problems faced by food banks. While food banks, as charitable organizations, often have very limited resources, and thus are in dire need to operate efficiently, their decision making is often complicated by the presence of various uncertainties. The volume of food donations to be collected generally only becomes known upon arrival at the donor locations, while the time spent on waiting and service usually depends on the size of the donations.

Table 7

Comparison of matheuristic results on the random instances for different standard deviations of demand. The average duration (columns Duration) is presented in hours, whereas the wall clock time (columns Time) is given in seconds.

Instance	$\sigma = 0$					$\sigma = 0.1\mu$					$\sigma = 0.2\mu$					$\sigma = 0.3\mu$				
	Data set	N	K	Duration	IP	Time	K	Duration	IP	Time	K	Duration	IP	Time	K	Duration	IP	Time		
c101	20	2	4.7	0	1	2	5.0	0	2	3	3.4	0	2	3	3.6	0	3			
	30	3	4.4	0	2	3	4.6	0	3	3	4.6	0	2	4	3.6	1	3624			
	40	4	4.9	0	3	4	5.1	0	205	5	4.2	1	3651	5	4.3	0	81			
	50	5	4.5	0	3	5	4.7	0	20	5	4.7	0	31	6	4.1	1	3637			
	60	6	4.7	0	6	6	5.0	0	725	7	4.4	1	3645	7	4.5	1	3823			
	70	7	4.9	0	6	7	5.1	0	686	8	4.6	1	4373	8	4.7	1	6237			
	80	8	4.8	0	8	8	5.0	0	535	9	4.5	1	3956	9	4.6	1	4101			
	90	9	4.8	0	10	9	5.0	0	789	10	4.6	1	4392	10	4.6	1	5565			
	100	10	4.8	0	10	10	5.1	0	2840	11	4.7	1	7271	11	4.8	1	5521			
	c201	20	2	5.2	0	16	2	5.2	0	17	2	5.1	0	9	2	5.1	0	9		
30		3	4.9	1	9	3	4.9	1	9	3	4.9	1	11	3	4.9	1	12			
40		3	6.8	0	96	3	6.9	0	50	3	6.8	0	39	4	5.3	1	97			
50		4	5.8	1	99	4	5.9	1	111	4	5.9	1	544	4	6.0	0	482			
60		4	7.4	0	301	5	5.7	1	320	5	5.8	1	1202	5	5.8	1	1018			
70		5	7.0	0	486	5	7.0	0	1018	6	5.8	1	4119	6	5.9	1	4534			
80		6	6.4	1	192	6	6.4	1	232	6	6.5	1	1307	6	6.5	1	1378			
90		6	7.1	0	175	6	7.2	0	394	7	6.3	1	3687	7	6.3	1	5430			
100		7	6.7	1	297	7	6.8	1	239	7	6.8	1	1878	7	6.9	1	2052			
r101		20	2	5.2	0	1	2	5.2	0	1	2	5.2	0	2	2	5.2	0	4		
	30	3	4.9	0	4	3	4.9	0	4	3	4.9	0	3	3	4.9	0	3			
	40	4	5.0	1	9	4	5.0	1	9	4	5.0	0	5	4	5.0	0	5			
	50	4	5.9	0	15	4	5.9	0	19	4	6.0	0	594	5	4.8	0	7			
	60	5	5.4	0	33	5	5.4	0	67	5	5.5	0	735	5	5.7	0	901			
	70	6	5.3	0	33	6	5.3	0	34	6	5.3	0	26	6	5.3	0	60			
	80	6	5.9	0	46	6	6.2	0	3774	7	5.1	0	44	7	5.2	0	2625			
	90	7	5.7	0	50	8	5.1	1	3644	8	5.1	0	241	8	5.2	0	3663			
	100	8	5.4	0	74	8	5.5	0	1385	9	4.9	1	4337	9	4.9	1	7314			
	Total		139	148.3	5	1985	141	149.0	7	17130	152	140.7	14	46105	156	137.5	15	62188		
Comparison to																				
Base case		91%	105%	36%	4%	93%	106%	50%	37%	100%	100%	100%	100%	103%	98%	107%	135%			
Deterministic case		100%	100%	100%	100%	101%	100%	140%	863%	109%	95%	280%	2323%	112%	93%	300%	3133%			

Table 8

Comparison of matheuristic results on the real-life instances for different standard deviations of demand. The average duration (columns Duration) is presented in hours, whereas the wall clock time (columns Time) is given in seconds.

Data set	$\sigma = 0$					$\sigma = 0.1\mu$					$\sigma = 0.2\mu$					$\sigma = 0.3\mu$				
	N	K	Duration	IP	Time	K	Duration	IP	Time	K	Duration	IP	Time	K	Duration	IP	Time			
Food Bank Zevenaar	7	2	2.2	0	0	2	2.2	0	0	2	2.2	0	0	2	2.2	0	0			
Food Bank Eemsdelta	8	2	2.1	1	1	2	2.1	0	1	2	2.1	0	0	2	2.1	0	0			
	9	2	2.8	0	0	2	2.8	0	1	2	2.8	0	1	2	2.8	0	1			
Moisson Montréal	34	6	7.0	0	2	6	7.0	0	62	7	6.0	1	3636	7	6.1	1	3762			
	41	7	6.7	1	232	7	6.7	0	264	7	6.8	0	1047	8	5.9	1	4608			
	42	8	7.0	1	5	8	7.0	0	616	9	6.2	1	4640	9	6.3	1	4780			
	43	6	7.5	0	3	7	6.4	1	4181	7	6.4	1	4314	7	6.4	0	1118			
	46	8	7.5	0	10	9	6.7	1	4859	9	6.7	1	7230	10	6.1	2	7991			
	46	6	7.8	0	6	7	6.8	1	4234	7	6.8	0	1348	8	6.0	1	4258			
Total		47	50.5	3	258	50	47.7	3	14217	52	46.1	4	22217	55	43.9	6	26518			
Comparison to																				
Base case		90%	110%	75%	1%	5200%	103%	75%	64%	100%	100%	100%	100%	106%	95%	150%	119%			
Deterministic case		100%	100%	100%	100%	106%	94%	100%	5504%	111%	91%	133%	8600%	117%	87%	200%	10265%			

These planning challenges of food banks give rise to the CVRP-SDSW, a multifaceted and highly complex stochastic optimization problem, that involves a number of strategic and operational decisions under consideration of several distinct types of uncertainty. To obtain a feasible solution to this problem, we developed a matheuristic that decomposes the problem into its individual decision components. This method first determines the number of districts, before allocating each customer to exactly one district and then planning a route for each district. Finally, a set of feedback mechanisms is applied to amend previous decisions when necessary. Throughout these components of the matheuristic, we make use of chance constraints to ensure that the probability of not meeting the vehicle capacity and travel time limit is below a specified level.

The performance of the matheuristic was evaluated using both an artificial data set based on the Solomon instances, as well as on

real-life data which were gathered from three food banks in the Netherlands and Canada. This extensive computational analysis reveals that the matheuristic yields feasible solutions within acceptable computing times on both the artificial and the real-life instances, with up to 100 customers. The results confirm that our matheuristic can assist food banks in obtaining solutions that optimize the fleet size and are efficient in terms of route cost. Furthermore, the effect of uncertainty on the performance of the matheuristic has been identified as well as the performance of the matheuristic in solving the deterministic counterpart of the problem. These experiments demonstrate that our matheuristic is able to cope with various levels of uncertainty. In addition, we observe that the number of districts, the computing time and the number of iterations increase with higher levels of uncertainty.

We believe it is important to continue building on these findings as richer data becomes available. This holds particularly true as data

in the food bank context are generally scarce, limiting the scientific insights that can be obtained. The emergence of more and higher quality data may for example lead to better estimations of service and waiting times, which in return allows to better capture reality, thus reducing the gap between science and practice. Moreover, enriched data on historic district designs and completed routes would enable a more comprehensive comparison between the presented strategic and operational solutions, and current practices. This would enhance the depth of findings regarding the performance and quality of the proposed solutions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Meike Reusken: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Gilbert Laporte:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Sonja U.K. Rohmer:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Frans Cuijssen:** Funding acquisition, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

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Appendix A. Tractable convex quadratic reformulation for constraints (9)

The reformulation we propose below for constraints (9) relies on the same reasoning and assumptions as introduced in Section 4.2.2. For ease of notation, we define

$$b_i = 2a + \sum_{h=1}^{\infty} a \left(h - \frac{1}{2} \right) q_{ih} \quad i \in N.$$

Substituting b_i in constraints (9) gives:

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} b_i \xi_i > T - \frac{c_{0jk} + c_{jk0}}{s} - \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \frac{\tilde{c}_{ik}}{s} \right) \leq \eta \quad k \in K. \quad (19)$$

The normal distribution is a stable distribution, which means that $\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} b_i \xi_i$ follows the same distribution as ξ_i with means $\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} b_i \mu_i$ and variances $\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik}^2 b_i^2 \sigma_i^2$. Using this property, constraints (19) admit the following reformulation for $k \in K$:

$$\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} b_i \mu_i + F^{-1}(1 - \eta) \sqrt{\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik}^2 b_i^2 \sigma_i^2} \leq T - \frac{c_{0jk} + c_{jk0}}{s} - \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \frac{\tilde{c}_{ik}}{s}, \quad (20)$$

where $F^{-1}(\cdot)$ denotes the inverse cumulative distribution function of ξ_i . To obtain a quadratic convex reformulation of inequality (20), we use the fact that $x_{ik}^2 = x_{ik}$, $i \in N$, $k \in K$, and we square both sides to eliminate the square root. This inequality can be squared under the conditions that $F^{-1}(1 - \eta) \sqrt{\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik}^2 b_i^2 \sigma_i^2} \geq 0$ and $T - (c_{0jk} + c_{jk0})/s - \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} (\tilde{c}_{ik})/s - \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} b_i \mu_i \geq 0$. The former condition holds trivially because its two factors are nonnegative, while the latter condition has to be imposed explicitly. Hence, inequality (20) is satisfied when enforcing the following constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} & (F^{-1}(1 - \eta))^2 \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} b_i^2 \sigma_i^2 + 2 \left(T - \frac{c_{0jk} + c_{jk0}}{s} \right) \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \left(\frac{\tilde{c}_{ik}}{s} + b_i \mu_i \right) \\ & - \left(\sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \left(\frac{\tilde{c}_{ik}}{s} + b_i \mu_i \right) \right)^2 \leq \left(T - \frac{c_{0jk} + c_{jk0}}{s} \right)^2 \quad k \in K \end{aligned}$$

$$T - \frac{c_{0jk} + c_{jk0}}{s} - \sum_{i \in N} x_{ik} \left(\frac{\tilde{c}_{ik}}{s} + b_i \mu_i \right) \geq 0 \quad k \in K.$$

Appendix B. Instance generation

B.1. The probability of h vehicles in the queue upon arrival

Parameter q_{ih} denotes the probability that h vehicles are waiting in the queue at the location of customer $i \in N$. The values of these parameters are randomly generated by relying on the following realistic assumptions: (i) there are always at most three vehicles in the queue upon arrival (i.e., $q_{ih} = 0$ for $h \geq 4$); and (ii) probabilities vary across customer locations and are likely to decrease with the number of vehicles in the queue.

To generate these probabilities, we randomly assigned all customers to one of four groups. For the customers within a group, a random sample is drawn from a truncated (> 0) normal distribution with means and standard deviations, as given in Table 9.

Table 9

Overview of the means (i.e., (·, ·)) and standard deviations (i.e., (·, ·)) of the normal distribution for each group. These normal distributions are used to generate the random sample for the probability q_{ih} of h queuing vehicles upon arrival at customer $i \in N$.

	$h = 1$	$h = 2$	$h = 3$
Group 1	(0.1, 0.02)	(0.05, 0.02)	(0.005, 0.002)
Group 2	(0.2, 0.05)	(0.1, 0.05)	(0.05, 0.05)
Group 3	(0.01, 0.01)	(0.001, 0.001)	(0, 0)
Group 4	(0.15, 0.1)	(0.002, 0.1)	(0.001, 0.1)

B.2. Real-life instances: Plots of historic collection demands

The matheuristic presented in this paper relies on a predetermined distribution of demand. To make an acceptable assumption regarding this distribution for the real-life instances, we have plotted historic collection demands for Food Bank Eemsdelta and Moisson Montréal, which are presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Distributions of historic collection demand for Food Bank Eemsdelta (left) for collections from two bakeries in June 2022, and for Moisson Montréal (right) for supermarket collections in February 2022. The x-axis indicates the collection demands in kg, and the y-axis shows the frequency of the demand occurrences.

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